

The Delegation of Authority and Accountability Matrix in Two-Tier Local Government: Designed to Reduce Overlapping and Shift-Of-Push-Against Responsibility

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ABSTRACT: This study focuses on the design and application of a decentralization-accountability matrix in the two-tiered local government model in Vietnam, which officially commenced operation on July 1, 2025. Building upon the RACI (Responsible – Accountable – Consulted – Informed) model in modern governance, the study proposes a framework for analyzing four core questions: “Who decides – Who implements – Who pays – Who is responsible” to identify and address three common errors in decentralization: overlapping authority, authority gaps, and mismatch between tasks and resources. The research results provide a highly applicable decentralization matrix framework for key public service groups such as land and construction, civil registration, social security, environment, and urban order management, thereby contributing to improved public administration efficiency and reduced administrative processing time.

KEYWORDS: Two-tier local government, decentralization matrix, accountability, RACI, public services

1. INTRODUCTION

From July 1, 2025, the two-tiered local government model will officially operate synchronously nationwide. This is a revolutionary step in the process of institutional reform and reorganization of the state apparatus from the central to the local level. Under the new model, local governments are organized into two tiers, eliminating the district level and leaving only the provincial and commune levels with a new scale. From July 1, 2025, Vietnam will apply the two-tiered government model, comprising provinces and communes, with 34 provinces and 3,321 communes nationwide (Nhan Dan Online, 2026).

The transition from a three-tiered to a two-tiered model has created urgent demands for redefining the authority, responsibilities, and resources between different levels of government. Practical experience has also highlighted a series of challenges that need addressing. First and foremost is the need to improve the institutional framework by redefining the boundaries of authority between the provincial and commune levels, avoiding overlapping or gaps in responsibilities. These challenges require an effective governance tool to identify and overcome bottlenecks in the decentralization system.

The primary goal is to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of state management and governance, while simultaneously implementing stronger decentralization and delegation of power to local governments to better serve the people. However, decentralization without a clearly defined accountability mechanism can lead to shirking responsibility, avoidance, or abuse of power. Therefore, this study proposes applying the decentralization-accountability matrix model as a key governance tool, going beyond general "decentralization/delegation of power" to build specific matrices for each group of public services, thereby clearly defining the tasks, authority, resources, and responsibilities of each level of government.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH OVERVIEW

2.1. The concept and nature of decentralization and delegation of authority in local governance.

Vertical (territorial) decentralization is the process by which the central government transfers a portion of its powers, responsibilities, and material resources to local governments. Accordingly, local governments are public legal entities that can independently decide on local issues based on legal regulations (Duong Bach Long, 2022). This reflects the trend of modernizing public administration, in which the autonomy and responsibility of local governments are increasingly emphasized.

The issue of decentralization and delegation of power is regulated in the 2013 Constitution, the 2015 Law on Government Organization, and the Law on Local Government Organization. Accordingly, the decentralization and delegation of power between the central and local governments are legal provisions aimed at defining tasks and powers for each level, so that management is clear, transparent, and effective (Duong Bach Long, 2022). This delegation must ensure consistency with the functions, authority, and actual conditions at each level of government.

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Tasks falling under the jurisdiction of local governments must be decided and implemented by local governments; promoting the autonomy and accountability of local governments (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025). This principle emphasizes that autonomy must go hand in hand with responsibility, and this is the philosophical foundation for designing the decentralization-accountability matrix.

Clearly defining the authority between central and local government agencies; and between provincial and commune-level local governments (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025). This requirement poses a challenge: how to ensure that this demarcation is not only clear on paper but also feasible in practice, without creating gray areas or bottlenecks in the operational process.

2.2. Accountability in Public Administration

Accountability is the acknowledgment of responsibility for all actions, products, decisions, or policies made by an authorized person in leading, managing, and performing their duties; it is linked to the obligation to report, explain, and justify the consequences caused. The obligation to be accountable means fulfilling the obligation to provide complete information, the obligation to justify the authorized person's actions in the past, present, or future, and accepting punishment if negative consequences result.

The term "accountability" should be understood as "attributable responsibility"—meaning that when something happens, responsibility can be attributed to that person, so that the authority can reward or punish the person authorized to do so. This is a crucial point in designing a governance system: without clear accountability, there cannot be a mechanism for evaluating performance, rewarding, or penalizing violations.

Within the framework of state operations, accountability is understood as the responsibility of public authorities that have received power from the people and set the goal of exercising power for the people, and simultaneously have the obligation to answer, explain, and be accountable for all their activities (Bui Thi Ngoc Mai, 2021). This view is consistent with the nature of the socialist rule of law state of Vietnam, where state power belongs to the people and state agencies must be accountable to the people.

Accountability must be a combination of two elements: accountability and responsibility. These two aspects of accountability are unified in a whole and cannot be considered in isolation (Bui Thi Ngoc Mai, 2021). This means that an effective system of delegation of authority must ensure that every assigned task has a clearly defined responsible party, and that party must have the obligation and ability to be accountable for the results of its performance.

Accountability means that competent agencies, organizations, units, and individuals must clarify information and provide timely and complete explanations regarding their decisions and actions in performing their assigned tasks and duties. This definition emphasizes proactive accountability – not waiting until a problem arises to provide explanations, but regularly and continuously providing information about the task performance process.

2.3. The RACI model in project management and its applicability to public administration.

A responsibility assignment matrix, or RACI matrix, is a project management technique that describes the responsibilities of various stakeholders in completing tasks or deliverables. The matrix assigns one of four responsibilities to each stakeholder in executing a deliverable: Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, and Informed. This model has been widely applied in business and project management; however, its application in public administration remains limited.

By clearly defining roles, a RACI matrix prevents decision-making bottlenecks and confusion in the approval process. When roles are ambiguous, critical decisions can be delayed, as team members might not know who holds final accountability. The RACI model eliminates this issue by ensuring that the individual responsible for approvals is clearly designated as Accountable. These benefits are particularly applicable to public administration systems, where ambiguity regarding roles and responsibilities often leads to delays in processing applications and shirking of responsibility.

Public sector organizations often have a complex structure, with a central IT department overseeing technology strategy and implementation, as well as individual agencies or departments with their own unique requirements and stakeholders. Coordinating between these various moving parts can be a significant challenge due to a number of factors (Andy Rivers and Ves Sathya, 2025). This observation accurately reflects the reality of Vietnam's public administration system, where coordination between different levels and sectors remains a major challenge.

A RACI chart is a simple matrix that clarifies who is responsible, accountable, consulted, and informed for every task in a project. It helps teams avoid confusion, streamline communication, and ensure everything goes smoothly. Its advantage lies in its simplicity and intuitiveness, helping all stakeholders understand their roles in each specific task.

3. CURRENT SITUATION OF DELEGATION OF POWER AND ACCOUNTABILITY IN THE TWO-TIER LOCAL GOVERNMENT MODEL

3.1. Legal framework for decentralization and delegation of authority in the new model

The administrative units of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam are organized into two levels: a) Provinces and centrally-administered cities (hereinafter referred to as the provincial level); b) Communes, wards, and special zones under the provincial level (hereinafter

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referred to as the commune level) (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025). A commune is an administrative unit in rural areas; a ward is an administrative unit in urban areas; and a special zone is an administrative unit in some strategically important islands established in accordance with geographical and natural conditions, population characteristics, and requirements for socio-economic development, national defense, and security (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025).

Promoting the decentralization and delegation of tasks and powers from central government agencies to local governments; clearly defining the authority of the People's Committee and the authority of the Chairman of the People's Committee at the provincial and commune levels; ensuring there is no duplication or overlap in tasks and powers between central and local government agencies, between local governments at different levels, and between agencies and organizations under local governments (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025). This is a fundamental principle stipulated in the Law on Organization of Local Government in 2025.

The government has issued 28 decrees on decentralization and delegation of authority; defining the jurisdiction between the government and local governments at two levels (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2026). These decrees cover almost all areas of state management, from justice, finance, industry and trade, construction, agriculture and environment to culture, sports and tourism, education and training. However, the existence of numerous regulations simultaneously poses challenges regarding consistency and uniformity in application.

Ensuring openness, transparency, accountability, and effective control of power, coupled with the responsibility of inspection, auditing, and supervision by competent authorities; establishing mechanisms for monitoring, evaluating, inspecting, and promptly adjusting the content of delegated authority and decentralization when the delegated authority, organization, or individual fails to effectively perform the assigned tasks and powers (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2025). This regulation reflects modern governance thinking, according to which delegation of authority is not a one-time assignment but a continuous process with supervision and adjustment.

3.2. Identifying three common types of errors in authorization.

Firstly, overlapping authority occurs when two levels of government are assigned to perform the same task or have the authority to make decisions on the same issue. This overlapping in the division of responsibilities manifests as ambiguity between different levels of government, leading to wasted resources and management disruptions (Le Van Tu, 2025). When multiple entities have authority, no one is truly ultimately responsible, and citizens and businesses have to navigate through many different channels to get things done.

Many laws, such as the Land Law, the Education Law, and health laws, have not been synchronously adjusted with the Law on Organization of Local Government in 2025, leading to overlapping in the division of tasks (Le Van Tu, 2025). This is a practical problem when the transition to a two-tier model is happening rapidly, while the system of specialized legal documents has not had time to be synchronously adjusted.

Secondly, the authority gap problem arises when issues occur but no level of authority is assigned clear responsibility for resolving them. Currently, the coordination mechanism between the provincial and commune levels lacks clarity, leading to overlapping or overlooked tasks (Le Van Tu, 2025). Especially in the context of the decommissioning of the district level, many tasks previously handled by the district level may become "ownerless" if not promptly defined.

Communes often have to wait for guidance from the province, reducing the proactiveness that the two-tier model aims for. Meanwhile, the transfer of tasks from the district level to the commune level requires a specific coordination mechanism to avoid overlapping and neglecting tasks (Le Van Tu, 2025). This gap is particularly dangerous because it can lead to a situation where people do not know where to go to resolve their issues, reducing trust in the public administration.

Thirdly, a resource mismatch occurs when tasks are assigned but not accompanied by sufficient allocation of human resources, finances, and necessary tools for implementation. Communes, with their limited capacity, often have to wait for guidance from the province, reducing the proactiveness that the two-tier model aims for (Le Van Tu, 2025). This shows that strong decentralization to the commune level must go hand in hand with strengthening its capacity.

The delineation of authority must "clearly define the content and scope of tasks and powers, avoiding duplication and overlap," and "be consistent with the practical capacity and resources of each level." The requirements for delineating authority must be transparent and feasible, aiming to improve management efficiency, reduce overlap, and ensure that communes have sufficient resources to implement them (Le Van Tu, 2025).

3.3. Current status of the two-tier model operation in the initial phase

From the beginning of the year to December 15, 2025, localities have reduced 709 provincial-level specialized agencies (a 60.3% reduction) and 8,289 district-level specialized agencies (100%). At the same time, 467 provincial-level specialized agencies and 9,916 commune-level specialized departments have been established under the new model and quickly put into operation (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2025). These figures demonstrate the enormous scale of administrative streamlining and the unprecedented speed of implementation.

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The entire country will establish 34 provincial-level administrative units (a reduction of 29 provinces and cities) and 3,321 commune-level administrative units (a reduction of 6,714 units, or 66.91%); and cease operations of 696 district-level administrative units (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2025). Such large-scale restructuring requires a clear system of decentralization to avoid disruption in the provision of public services.

Ministries and sectors, in coordination with localities, will continue to streamline the organizational structure of administrative units after reorganization; and urge People's Committees at all levels to promptly issue specific regulations on the functions, tasks, and organizational structure of specialized agencies under the People's Committees at the provincial and commune levels according to the new model, ensuring clear responsibilities, clear tasks, and avoiding overlapping or omitted functions and tasks (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2025). The requirement of "clear responsibilities, clear tasks" is the foundation for building a matrix of decentralization and accountability.

Local authorities have deployed and seconded nearly 4,000 officials and civil servants to strengthen the commune level; and organized thousands of training and professional development courses (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2025). This shows the awareness of the need to improve the capacity of the commune level, however, a mechanism is still needed to ensure that this capacity is used effectively.

4. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR DELEGATION OF AUTHORITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY

4.1. Theoretical basis and design principles

This study proposes applying the RACI model, adapted to the context of Vietnamese public administration, to construct a matrix of decentralization and accountability. The RACI model brings structure and clarity to describing the roles that stakeholders play within a project. The RACI matrix clarifies responsibilities and ensures that everything the project needs done is assigned to someone to do it (CIO, 2025). The structure and clarity provided by the RACI model are fully applicable to defining roles among different levels of local government.

Responsible: People or stakeholders who perform the work. They must complete the task or objective or make the decision. Several people can be jointly responsible. **Accountable:** Person or stakeholder who is the "owner" of the work. He or she must sign off or approve when the task, objective, or decision is complete (CIO, 2025). In the context of public administration, "Responsible" can be understood as the agency/level that performs the specific task, while "Accountable" is the agency/level that is ultimately responsible for the outcome.

Based on the RACI framework, the study proposes a model of four core questions for each administrative procedure or public service:

The first question, "Who decides?" aims to determine which level of authority has the final say on the issue in question. This is equivalent to the "Accountable" role in the RACI model, with the principle that only one entity is ultimately responsible for each decision.

The second question, "Who implements it?" aims to determine which level of authority directly carries out the work, receives applications, processes them, and delivers results to citizens. This is equivalent to the "Responsible" role in the RACI model, which can involve multiple entities.

The third question, "Who pays?" aims to determine which budget sources are used to ensure the necessary conditions for task execution. This is a particularly important factor in the public sector, because without accompanying financial resources, task assignment becomes merely a formality.

The fourth question, "Who is accountable?" aims to identify the entity responsible for reporting, explaining, and bearing the consequences of the task's performance. In many cases, this entity coincides with the "decision-making" entity, but a separation may be necessary.

4.2. Principles of matrix design to mitigate authorization errors

Principle number one: One task – One person ultimately responsible. Success requires that there is only one person accountable, which means that "the buck stops there." (CIO, 2025). This principle ensures that there is no "nobody's responsibility" – each task must have one and only one level of ultimate accountability for the results. When problems arise, it is immediately clear who is responsible and accountable.

The second principle: Delegation of tasks must be accompanied by the allocation of resources. The agency or individual delegating authority is responsible for ensuring the necessary conditions for carrying out the delegated tasks and powers, except in cases where the delegated agency, organization, unit, or individual requests and independently ensures the conditions for carrying out the delegated tasks and powers (Dan Tri Online Newspaper, 2025). This principle overcomes the "resource mismatch" error by requiring the delegating authority to ensure the necessary conditions for implementation.

Third principle: Assign tasks to the level closest to the people and most effective in resolving issues. Clearly define the tasks and powers of local governments at each level based on the principle that "the local government at the level that can resolve issues

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more practically and effectively should be the one to carry them out." This principle aims to bring public services closer to the people and reduce intermediate layers.

Fourth principle: Complete decentralization, avoiding fragmentation of procedures. While highly appreciating the significant reduction in administrative procedures, the Deputy Prime Minister emphasized the requirement for complete decentralization; the agency that grants the license must carry out all related administrative procedures, avoiding overlap between the central and local levels (Vietnamplus Online Newspaper, 2025). This principle prevents a procedure from being fragmented into many levels, forcing citizens to go through multiple bureaucratic hurdles.

Fifth principle: Periodic review and adjustment. Continue to promote rational and effective decentralization and delegation of power. Strong decentralization and delegation of power must promote the initiative and creativity of localities, while ensuring uniformity in law enforcement, coupled with strengthened inspection, supervision, guidance, and support from ministries and agencies (Government Electronic Newspaper, 2025). This principle reflects flexible governance thinking, according to which the power distribution matrix is not immutable but needs to be adjusted as practical requirements demand.

4.3. Functional map between the two levels according to public service sectors

Based on the theoretical framework and design principles presented, the study proposes a detailed decentralization map for five key public service groups.

Group 1: Land and Construction Sector

This is a highly complex field that frequently generates complaints and lawsuits. In the two-tiered model, the division of authority needs to ensure the principle of centralizing strategic, inter-regional decisions at the provincial level, while routine administrative procedures are decentralized to the commune level.

Regarding the issuance of land use right certificates to households and individuals, following the principle of being "closest to the people," the commune level receives applications, verifies land origin, and prepares cadastral records. The provincial level issues the decision to grant the certificate and bears ultimate responsibility for its legality. Financial resources come from the provincial budget, with allocations to the communes to ensure operation.

Regarding the issuance of building permits for individual houses, the commune level receives applications, checks compliance with the detailed planning, and issues permit decisions. The provincial level issues the planning, provides general guidance, and supervises the process. Accountability rests with the Chairman of the People's Committee at the commune level.

Regarding land dispute resolution, the commune-level authorities conduct grassroots mediation as prescribed. If mediation fails, the provincial level receives the case and issues a decision. The final responsibility for the dispute resolution decision rests with the provincial level.

Group 2: Civil registration and residence sector

This is the group of services with the highest frequency of contact with the public, requiring speed and convenience. Strong decentralization to the commune level is therefore appropriate.

Regarding birth registration, marriage registration, and death registration, the commune level handles the entire process from receiving and verifying the information to issuing the certificate. The provincial level manages the database, issues forms, and provides operational guidance. The commune budget covers regular operating costs. Accountability rests with the commune-level judicial and civil registration officials and the Chairman of the Commune People's Committee.

Regarding permanent and temporary residence registration, in the context of digital transformation and the development of a national population database, the commune level receives applications and updates them into the system. The provincial level manages the centralized data system and handles complex cases. Central and provincial budgets ensure the technological infrastructure.

Group 3: Social Security Sector

Social security policies require accuracy in identifying beneficiaries and timeliness in payments. Decentralization needs to strike a balance between the need for strict control to prevent losses and the need for convenience for citizens.

Regarding the assessment of poor and near-poor households, the commune level organizes surveys and assessments within the community and compiles a list of proposed households. The provincial level approves the official list and allocates the support budget. The commune level is responsible for the accuracy of the assessment process, while the provincial level is responsible for the final decision.

Regarding the payment of social welfare benefits, the commune level compiles monthly payment lists and organizes direct payments to beneficiaries. The provincial level transfers the budget and conducts inspections and supervision. The commune level is accountable for ensuring payments are made to the correct beneficiaries on time.

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Group 4: Environmental Sector

Environmental management is characterized by many issues that are inter-regional and inter-communal in nature, requiring coordination and collaboration from higher levels. However, regular monitoring activities often require the participation of the grassroots level.

Regarding environmental permits for small-scale production and business establishments, the commune level receives applications, conducts preliminary assessments, and reports to the provincial level. The provincial level conducts the official assessment and issues the permit. The responsibility for the permit decision rests with the provincial level.

Regarding the handling of environmental violations within the commune, the commune level detects, records, and handles violations within its jurisdiction. The provincial level handles serious violations that exceed the commune's authority. The budget for inspection and monitoring activities comes from the commune budget, with support from the provincial budget.

Regarding the management of household solid waste, the commune level organizes collection and transportation according to a plan approved by the provincial level. The provincial level plans treatment sites, organizes bidding for services, and monitors quality. Funding comes from sanitation fees and the provincial budget.

Group 5: Urban Order Management

For wards (administrative units in urban areas), managing urban order is an ongoing task that requires quick response and close contact with the field.

Regarding construction order management, commune/ward levels conduct regular inspections, detect and handle minor violations, and report serious cases to the provincial level. The provincial level directs the enforcement of regulations against serious violations. The responsibility for timely detection rests with the commune level, while the responsibility for definitively resolving major violations rests with the provincial level.

Regarding sidewalk and road management, the commune/ward level directly manages and handles violations within its jurisdiction. The provincial level issues general regulations and provides support forces when necessary. Revenue from sidewalk usage fees is decentralized to the commune.

5. AUTHORITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY MATRIX: FRAMEWORK AND APPLICATION

5.1. Proposed matrix structure

Based on the four core questions model, the study proposes the following structure for the accountability-responsibility matrix. The matrix is designed as a table with columns representing the four main components: Decision, Execution, Resources, and Accountability. The rows represent each specific administrative procedure or public service in each field.

For each cell in the matrix, it is necessary to clearly identify: the competent authority (provincial or commune level), the specific agency responsible (People's Committee, which specialized agency), and the specific job title (Chairman of the People's Committee, Head of Department, specialized civil servant). This specificization ensures the principle of "clear person, clear task".

Expect some overlaps and dependencies, and ensure there is always one accountable individual per task. This person acts as the task-level "project lead," driving the process to avoid having more than one person in charge. [This principle](#), applied to public administration, means that each procedure/service must have a clearly defined "primary person in charge" within the matrix.

5.2. Matrix illustration for the land and construction sector

To illustrate how the matrix is applied, the study details the matrix for several procedures in the land and construction sector, one of the most complex fields.

Regarding the procedure for issuing land use right certificates for the first time to households and individuals, the authority to sign the certificate rests with the Chairman of the Provincial People's Committee (or the Director of the Department of Natural Resources and Environment, who is authorized to do so). Regarding the Implementation component, the commune receives the application at the One-Stop Service Center; the commune's land cadastral officer verifies the land's origin, gathers community opinions, and prepares the application for submission to the provincial level; the provincial level (Land Registration Office) appraises the application, submits it for signing, and returns the results. Regarding the Resource component, the provincial budget covers the operating costs of the Land Registration Office, and the budget allocated to the commune ensures the operation of the land cadastral officer and the One-Stop Service Center. Regarding the Explanation component, the commune's land cadastral officer is responsible for the accuracy of the verification information; the Chairman of the Commune People's Committee is responsible for completing the application within the deadline; and the Director of the Land Registration Office is responsible for the decision to issue the certificate.

Regarding the procedure for granting building permits for individual houses in urban areas, the authority to issue permits rests with the Chairman of the People's Committee at the commune (ward) level. Regarding the implementation, the commune-level land and construction official receives the application, checks its conformity with the detailed planning, and submits it to the Chairman of the People's Committee for signing and granting the permit. The provincial level (Department of Construction) issues the plan,

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provides professional guidance, and conducts inspections and audits. Regarding resources, the permit fee is collected by the commune and a portion is retained to ensure operation; the provincial budget supports planning and inspection work. Regarding accountability, the Chairman of the People's Committee at the commune level bears ultimate responsibility for the legality of the issued permit, while the professional official is responsible for the accuracy of the application review.

5.3. Matrix Construction and Operation Process

For the decentralization and accountability matrix to be effective, it needs to adhere to a systematic construction and operation process.

The first step is to review all administrative procedures and public services in each sector. This needs to be based on current legal documents and the practical operation of the locality. Deputy Prime Minister Pham Thi Thanh Tra requested a review of the entire system of legal documents, thoroughly addressing overlapping and inconsistencies with the two-tiered local government model (Vietnamplus Online Newspaper, 2025).

The second step is to clearly define the four components for each procedure/service, ensuring there are no gaps and no overlaps. Here's something every project manager knows: Even the best plan fails when roles are unclear. Ineffective decision-making is one of the biggest reasons projects stall. [13](#) Unclear role assignments are a major cause of project delays.

The third step is to conduct extensive consultations with stakeholders, including provincial-level specialized agencies, commune-level People's Committees, implementing officials, and representatives of the people. If team members are not involved in the creation of a RACI chart, they may be less likely to buy into the roles and responsibilities assigned to them. [22](#) Stakeholder participation ensures feasibility and consensus in implementation.

The fourth step is to make the matrix public and organize training for all relevant stakeholders. The matrix should be publicly posted on the Public Service Portal so that citizens can be aware of and monitor it.

The fifth step is to periodically review and adjust the matrix. This means the roles and responsibilities are going to change as your organization matures. It's better to schedule a 3-month, 6-month, and 12-month review of the RACI ahead of time instead of waiting until there's an organizational conflict that needs to be resolved. Regular reviews ensure the matrix always accurately reflects reality and is adjusted promptly when problems arise.

6. SOLUTIONS TO IMPROVE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING THE DELEGATION OF AUTHORITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY MATRIX

6.1. Improving institutions and legal documents

Reviewing and amending regulations will help strengthen the capacity of commune-level governments, ensuring that administrative processes and procedures are consistent with the reality and capabilities of commune-level administrative units, while creating uniformity and consistency in the authority and responsibility of each level of government. Therefore, in the current context, parallel to the process of reorganizing administrative units, it is necessary to review regulations on decentralization and delegation of power in state management in general, and in resolving administrative procedures in particular (Nguyen Dang Phuong Truyen, 2025).

There is an urgent need to issue specific guidelines on the development and application of the decentralization and accountability matrix at the local level. These guidelines should clearly define the principles, development process, methods of public disclosure, and mechanisms for monitoring and adjusting the matrix.

When only the provincial and commune levels remain, regulations on handling administrative procedures need to be reviewed to eliminate complex processes, reduce overlaps, and improve transparency in handling work (Nguyen Dang Phuong Truyen, 2025). Simplifying processes is a prerequisite for the decentralization matrix to be effective.

6.2. Enhancing the capacity of commune-level authorities

Quang Ngai, Gia Lai, and Dak Lak provinces have identified the training and improvement of the quality of commune-level officials, civil servants, and public employees as the "key" to the stable operation of the two-tiered local government system, both in the short and long term (Vietnamplus Online Newspaper, 2025). Training and development should be linked to a specific power distribution matrix so that commune-level officials clearly understand their assigned tasks and methods of implementation.

Ineffective oversight increases the risk of abuse of power or corruption at the local level, especially when officials are not adequately trained in legal responsibilities. Therefore, alongside improving professional skills, it is necessary to strengthen education on public service responsibilities and accountability for commune-level officials.

6.3. Promoting digital transformation and technology application

Decrees need to clearly demonstrate the requirements for digital transformation, integration of online public services, and facilitating convenience for citizens and businesses (Vietnamplus Online Newspaper, 2025). The authorization matrix needs to be integrated into the data management system and electronic processes, so that monitoring and supervision are carried out automatically and transparently.

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The city of Hue has identified digital government as a strategic tool to ensure "smoothness" and centralized management in the two-tiered local government model (Vietnamplus Online Newspaper, 2025). This experience shows that digital transformation is not only a tool but also a prerequisite for the effective operation of the two-tiered model.

6.4. Strengthening oversight and accountability

Whenever there is a ranking or assessment of administrative quality, for example through the Provincial Competitiveness Index (PCI) or the Provincial Public Administration and Governance Performance Index (PAPI), the head of the relevant public administration must be accountable to the local public (Nguyen Quoc Suu, 2022). Connecting the decentralization matrix with performance evaluation indicators will create an objective monitoring mechanism and an incentive for improvement.

Regulations are needed to strengthen the authority and responsibility of leaders based on the principle of "assigning responsibility must be linked to assigning authority." This principle needs to be concretized in the power distribution matrix, ensuring that those assigned responsibility have sufficient authority and resources to fulfill their tasks.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study proposes a theoretical framework and practical tools for constructing a decentralization-accountability matrix in the two-tiered local government model in Vietnam. The research results show that applying the RACI model, adapted to the Vietnamese public administration context through four core questions – "Who decides – Who implements – Who pays – Who is responsible" – can help identify and address three common types of decentralization errors: overlapping authority, authority gaps, and mismatch between tasks and resources.

The implementation of the two-tiered local government model marks the beginning of a new phase in administrative reform, enhancing governance capacity and building strong public trust in the government apparatus. This is not merely a formal improvement, but a fundamental change in the way the state operates – prioritizing the people, using efficiency as a measure, and driving modernization and integration.

The matrix of decentralization and accountability, as a modern governance tool, will contribute to realizing these goals. By clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of each level and entity in each administrative procedure and public service, the matrix helps minimize buck-passing and avoidance, while creating a basis for citizens and businesses to monitor the activities of the public administration.

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that competent authorities consider issuing specific guidelines on the construction and application of the decentralization and accountability matrix at the local level, integrating this matrix into the e-government public service management system, and incorporating it into training and professional development programs for civil servants. Simultaneously, a mechanism for periodically evaluating the effectiveness of the matrix and making timely adjustments as needed is necessary, ensuring that the matrix remains a "living" tool effectively serving local governance.

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